

Review On Indigenous crafts in Boat Building of Indian Sundarbans

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Abstract: *The geographical environment of the lower Gangetic delta played an important role in determining the livelihood of the marginal people. So, the people of that region mastered various arts and crafts over generation to form a social entity. Among the indigenous boat building became very necessary. Due to the abundance of waterways over land in Sundarbans, which has a vast expanse of water, and depending on the technical needs and suggestions of watercraft in terms of means of transportation, transportation of goods, shing, its transportation and preservation, naval craftsmen used to build different types of boats, small and large, according to their needs. However, there were environmental and tribal differences in the process of boat building. However, rafts made of banana trees and boats made of wood were widely used in riverine waters since ancient times. 'Rabbing' and 'caulking' methods were particularly used in the construction of shing boats. However, due to the lack of discussion on important technical issues in indigenous boat building, the main objective of the present article is to shed light on the undisputed issue.*

Keywords: *Indian Sundarbans, naval construction, use of boats, indigenous crafts, different types of boats.*

The Sundarbans is the world's largest vegetated forest region from West Bengal (India) to Bangladesh. 'O' Maley in his report points out that Clive included 24 mahals of this region in the zamindari of Calcutta in accordance with the interim agreement between the East India Company and Mirzafar.¹ Then Warren Hastings made a separate district with these 24 quarters. Since, then this region was originally identified as 24 Parganas. However, the district was also known as 'Athero Bhatir Desh'. But the place was called Sundarbans because of the proximity of sea and coast.² Farminger's report expressively considered it appropriate to refer to this region by the terms Sundari and Sundarbans.³ Triangular plain delineates the Sundarbans as its northern boundary by the Dampier-Hodges line, with Bangladesh in the east, Bay of Bengal in the south, Hooghly River flowing in the west. The total area is 8000 square meters.⁴

Since ancient times, rivers have been considered as a means of transportation in aquatic environments for transport in goods, trade, shing, etc and hence the urge to improve the watercraft was felt.⁵ It is noteworthy that there was a close relationship between the boats and the aquatic people of the Gangetic South Bengal consisting of rivers, creeks and canals. Even the spiritual connection of the people of the coastal areas of the Ganges with boats is captured in Charyagiti. Besides, naval industry is mentioned in the books of the Rigveda, Vayupurana, Markandeya Purana, Baudhayana Dharmasutra, Ramayana Mahabharata etc. Any way as from the source of discussion about indigenous boat building, the main topic of the article, it is said that, at the primary level, fish collectors use a tree trunk as a boat to catch fish or used tree trunks as poles. This style of naval art is divided into two parts: in the first place, People used to burn a part of the trunk of the tree and make a boat by making a hole with a stone-built device. Another group of people. A few wooden logs were put together to make rafts.⁶

Boats were one of the vehicles used on the waterways of the vast expanse of water. In this case, the use of indigenously built standing or propelled boats is gen-

erally common in the east of Matla such as Vidyadhari, Gosaba, Raimangal, Ichamati, Kalagachia, Kalindi, Saptamukhi, Thakuran.⁷ However, we get to know from statistics that 5948 boats built in indigenous technology are known to be used in Diamond Harbour, Patharpratima, Namkhana, Kakdwip west of Matla.^{7a}

Of course, rafts are the oldest means of shing, followed by canoes. Rafts were made from a variety of readily available materials. Among these, the main ingredients are banana tree and sola. 10-12 banana trees are tightly joined together to make a raft. Inverted earthen pots tied to bamboo structures were also used as rafts in calm waters.⁸ Donga was the traditional ancient water craft of Bengal. Mainly palm trees were used to make rafts. Big palm trees were dug up from the ground with the base and cut to size towards the base and holes were made to make canoes. The space in front was closed with wood. However, more than 2-3 people could not ride together. Pushed by bamboo logs, small canals, lakes, water-logged paddy elds were crossed with the help of the canoes. However, it cannot be said that there is no use of canoes at present. Somewhere in the villages, the use of canoes attracts attention. Besides, the fishermen used canoes made of sal trees.⁹ In terms of construction techniques and technology, the canoes are almost identical with 30 feet in length and 3 feet in width. Currently, women in the Sundarbans region are found to collect fish and crabs with a small canoe at the mouth of the river.¹⁰ They could easily enter the inlet by canoe on the inland water bodies.

Along with the development of civilization, people used to make boats in the river side ports to make the waterways easier and safer. Later, however, iron nails and screws took the place of wooden pegs. However, because the boat made in this way is unsuitable for use in salt water; The planks of the boat were made of jute, wood ash, betel bark and the juice extracted from the fruit using a combination of indigenous technology. The boats made in this way were much more durable, and so it became usable.¹¹ And the popularity of boats built with caulking technology was increased. Besides, planks were stitched together with coconut shells. To make the boat water-tight, the whole part was fitted with bulrushes made of hemp.^{11a}

Dr. Ramaswamy Naidu's report on the status of fisheries in undivided Bengal states that the boats without instruments suitable to the environment and climate are: Dingi or Jelle Dingi, Chandi boat, Bachari boat, Big Balam and Small Balam etc. Assam sal, teak and jarul wood were mainly used to make these boats. He also mentioned that at that time the daily wage of a naval crafts man was 1 rupee including food.¹²

The details of the said boats will be discussed in order:

Jele Dinghy: The most common type of boat used for fishing waters adjacent to coastal areas is the 'jeledinghy'. Boats in the Gangetic delta region had no room for luxury. Canopies were used only during monsoons. The vessel is 25 to 30 feet long and 4feet wide, with a bamboo mast. There are two sailors at either end of the canoe. One sits back and holds the tiler, the other sits on the side. The carrying capacity of this boat is 14-15 quintals.¹³ A triangular net was used in the boat.¹⁴ The boats were mainly made of sal, teak, local khirish and acasia wood by the poor fishermen of the South Twenty-four Parganas. The expenditure of making such boats was very low.¹⁵ As the planks of the boat were of narrow shape (2.5-4 cm), one plank was joined to the other. Apart from shing, these canoes were also used for other purposes. For example, by anchoring a boat in a large river or sea, only the necessary equipment, food, water, and basic medical supplies were kept. Ca-

noes were very useful for shing in canals or narrow canals, because when the boat reached the end of the canal, when the fish were gathered together, the fish were collected from there and the fish were separated according to the type of fish.¹⁶

Chadi Boats: Among the boats used by fishermen, Chadi Boats were more attractive than other boats in terms of structure and size. Two or more sailors steered the boat with the help of a stand. The staves usually have bamboo handles with blades of sal wood. The blade is flat on one side, convex on the other. After the name of this boat, the user net is also named Chadi net. Hilsa fishing was practiced with this net. Generally, 4 quintals of fish can be kept in a Jele Dinghy whereas 15-16 quintals of fish can be kept in a Chadi Boat as the boats are 80-100feet long and 5-6feet wide. Due to the large size of the boats, casting net became easier in the far areas from the coast.¹⁷ This net was not woven by the fishermen of the Gangetic delta region. If the net was torn, they would immediately buy a new net without repairing it. The net was 200 inches long and 100 inches wide.¹⁸

Bachari Boat: The contribution of Bachari boat was very popular among fishermen. Boats are 30-50 feet in length and 3-6 feet wide. This boat was named after a type of net called Bachari. More than four sailors were needed to operate the boat. Another type of boat called

MechhoBachari is mentioned in fish marketing.¹⁹ This boat is popularly known as fish boat. Boats had separate decks for keeping fish. The fish were separated by light. Wooden walls to keep them alive. Two sailors stood at the ends of the boat with large oval at paddles and steered the boat forward. There is a similar stand attached to the roof of the chai or to the back bar of the chai, known as 'jal hal'.²⁰ The main sailor holds the steer to control the change of the course of the boat. Dri nets, bag nets, dip nets were used as materials.²¹ Generally, this boat is used to catch fish in the coastal areas, estuaries, river banks.²² Of course, these boats had masts, and the sails were hoisted when necessary.²³

Balam: Balam was a particular type of boat that had a special contribution for shing in the ocean. This boat was bigger, both in length and width, than other boats. Being 30-45 feet in length and 4-10 feet in width, its carrying capacity was high. It could carry about 100-300 quintals of fish or other goods at the same time.²⁴ Originally, this boat was named an era type of rice. The sides of the boat were built higher to transport more cargo. In the boat, the oar, sail, guna and stand were used by the sailor himself.²⁵ But the shing boats in the sea near the estuary were lighter and smaller in size. In this case, according to the technical needs, the village leaders used to build boats.²⁶ Native fishermen have gained technical fame in this industry since ancient times, but this has been denied by Orientalists like James Hornel. However, like net making, ecological and ethnic differences are noticeable in the construction and use of boats such.²⁷ Currently, the use of Balam boats in the region has largely declined. The new generation is showing reluctance as boat building is not a lucrative profession.²⁸

Pansi: Pansi is a boat with a large shade and is made of Sundari, Garana, Gewa, Arjuna wood. Although this boat was coming into existence during the British period, the use of the boat was noticeable in the later period and in the Gangetic region. Pansi gained popularity in passenger transport due to its multiple rooms. Pansi is even known to be used in social events like weddings. The boat, 25-30 feet in length and 5-7.5 feet in width, was used on river banks with the help of stand and oars.²⁹ In the construction of these boats, bamboo planks were cut into narrow pieces and used as the timber for the rafters.³⁰

Canoe Boats and Khil Boats: These boats were made of sal wood brought from Balagarh and the use of these boats is notable at Kulpi, Diamond Harbour, Falta, Nodakhali regions. These boats are 40-50 feet in length, 13-14 feet in width and 5½feet in depth. These are used for passenger transportation, cargo transportation and shing. Financially backward fishermen use these boats to collect sand from the forage for additional income, apart from coastal shing.³¹

Dingy and Poukha: The use of this boat, made of shall and Ashna wood, was essential for the crab fishermen. Its length is 27-32 feet, width 5 feet and depth 2.5 feet.³² Structural differences are observed between canoes and Poukha. The lower part of the canoe is round, the bottom of the Poukha is at. The crab catchers of Tarda and Pratapnagar in the twenty-four parganas have continued to build canoes and poukhas in the native manner.³³

Ferry boats: According to the official estimate there are about 123 ferry wharves in the Sundarbans region adjacent to the delta. Apart from this, there are several ferries scattered in different places. From there also many people use this watercraft as a means of daily commuting. According to the experience of local sailors, more than 1500 boats are engaged in passenger transport. As several bridges were built in the contemporary period.³⁴ The problems of the people of this region have been solved to a large extent.

Finally, it can be said that the marginal people of this region have to rely entirely on indigenous watercraft for transportation. On the other hand, fishermen, moulas and wood cutters areal dependent on indigenous boats to earn their livelihood in the geographical and natural environment. As a result, the naval industry has developed based on the production of various types of domestic boats. We can't deny the important role of the boats, built in indigenous technology, in the social life.

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